

Next Generation Linear Algebra: One Singular Value Decomposition to Catch Them All across Data Size, Precision, and Hardware

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Abstract—The Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) is a foundational building block in many applications, including low-rank adaptation (LoRA) for large language models (LLMs). Historically, separate SVD implementations have been designed for each data precision, for each hardware vendor, and for each hardware type (personal computer and HPC). This divergence leads to increased development time, the need to redevelop entire libraries when new architectures or data types emerge, and significant complexity for the end user. In this abstract, we discuss a work in progress to develop an alternative: a unified SVD, enabled by abstraction layers. We demonstrate that state-of-the-art performance across the board can be reached using abstraction frameworks, and investigate the performance engineering process and the characteristics that enable adaptable performance.

I. INTRODUCTION: DON’T COPY CODE, USE ABSTRACTIONS. DO NOT SACRIFICE PERFORMANCE.

The Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) is a foundational building block in many high-performance computing (HPC) applications due to its rank-revealing properties. Recently, it has attracted increasing attention through its use in low-rank adaptation (LoRA) techniques for large language models (LLMs) [18]. Most application libraries (e.g., PyTorch [15]) rely on GPU vendor-specific libraries such as `cuSOLVER`, `rocSOLVER`, or `oneMKL`, each requiring separate implementations for different hardware architectures and data precisions. These libraries are typically limited to GPU-resident, single-node execution, making them unsuitable for multicore or distributed-memory HPC environments that are essential for large-scale datasets. To address these limitations, specialized libraries have been developed for scalability and performance: `MAGMA` [1] for GPU acceleration, `PLASMA` [11] for shared-memory multicore systems, and `SLATE` [12] for heterogeneous and distributed environments. However, as hardware complexity increases, the number of required implementations grows [14]. This specialization comes at a cost: it increases development and maintenance effort and often necessitates full redevelopment when new hardware platforms, data types [4], or mixed-precision strategies [7] are introduced.

In this work, we propose an alternative: an SVD implementation designed within an abstract framework to achieve maximal separation between algorithm and hardware. Our approach enables a single codebase that is agnostic to data precision, hardware vendor, and data size—factors that traditionally dictate separate implementations due to communication and performance constraints. We implement this in the Julia programming language, leveraging its multiple dispatch and type inference capabilities [6]. Abstract functions are specialized and optimized at compile-time through LLVM, enabling hardware-specific code generation from a unified high-level implementation. For example, the `GPUArrays.jl` abstraction [5] uses type inference to generate accelerator-optimized intermediate representations (IR),

such as NVPTX for NVIDIA GPUs, via LLVM backends. Furthermore, `KernelAbstractions.jl` [9] provides a unified interface for writing GPU kernels across different hardware platforms, facilitating portable and vendor-independent execution. This abstraction framework allows our SVD implementation to remain performant across GPU architectures while avoiding code duplication and vendor lock-in.

The contributions of this thesis work-in-progress are:

- **Hardware- and precision-agnostic SVD implementation.** We develop a unified SVD implementation that is adaptable and future-proof: new data precisions, hardware types, and vendor-specific architectures can be seamlessly integrated without requiring full redevelopment. We demonstrate that high-level abstractions in Julia can achieve state-of-the-art performance, and we describe how to design such abstractions for performance portability.
- **Open-source performance-engineered library.** We release our software as open-source [2]. Unlike many proprietary GPU-resident linear algebra libraries (e.g., `cuSOLVER`, `oneMKL`), our implementation makes the design space of GPU kernel optimization transparent. This enables reuse through direct integration into abstraction-based frameworks [14], or as a standalone backend library in larger codebases [3].
- **Lowering the barrier to HPC for all scientists.** Where large-scale SVD previously required specialized knowledge of multiple HPC libraries and cluster-specific tuning, we propose a single, high-level function that runs unmodified on both consumer laptops and heterogeneous HPC clusters. This dramatically improves usability and accessibility, allowing non-HPC experts to harness advanced compute resources.

This work is inspired by recent publications demonstrating that performance and portability can go hand-in-hand for GPU-resident singular value decomposition, and triangular matrix operations [8], [17], [19]. We extend these principles further toward out-of-core execution [16].

II. RESEARCH PLAN: MULTI-SCALE INTEGRATION

In the initial phase we start by performance engineering the SVD on GPUs, then we extend the work to out-of-core and multi-GPU settings, and finally we integrate full multicore capabilities. Critical to achieving highly performant abstractions is determining the required abstraction parameters, and the level at which abstractions can be integrated.

a) *Background: QR-based two-stage algorithm.* The well-known QR-based two-stage SVD [13] can be summarized as follows (Algorithm 1, Figure 1): for every diagonal tile, calculate householder reflectors that renders the tile upper diagonal and the columns below zero, or annihilates

them, the so-called panel factorization. Then apply these householder reflectors to the remainder of the matrix. In this work, we denote the joint application of these two functions as GETSMQRT, a joining of the names of corresponding LAPACK-functions GEQRT, UNMQR, TSQRT, TSMQR. Repeat this process transposed to render the tile to the right of the diagonal tile lower diagonal and tiles to its right zero, and apply these transformations to the rest of the matrix. Repeat for every tile. In Algorithm 1, we leverage the lazy transpose operator to apply the function to the inverted indices of the original matrix, without physically transposing the data layout, similarly reducing the amount of needed functions by a factor two.

Fig. 1. Classic two-stage QR-based singular value decomposition. For each diagonal tile, apply an orthogonal transformation that makes the tile upper triangular and annihilates the column below. Subsequently, transform the tile to the right of the diagonal into a lower triangular form and annihilate the row to its right. Figure from [17].

Algorithm 1 Julia: stage one of QR-based SVD, from [17]

```
function banddiag!(A::GPUorLargeMatrix{T}, Tau::
  AbstractGPUMatrix{T}, N::Int, backend) where T
  for k in 1:(N-1)
    GETSMQRT!(A, Tau, k, N, backend)
    GETSMQRT!(A', Tau, k, N, backend, "LQ")
  end
  GETSMQRT!(A, Tau, N, N, backend)
end
```

b) *Abstractions over hardware settings:* Achieving GPU-resident and GPU-accelerated performance follow a very similar pattern with respect to communication: in the GPU-resident version the matrix is stored in GPU memory, and the tiles are loaded row-by-row into L1 memory of the GPU multiprocessors, while in the CPU-resident, GPU-accelerated version, the tiles are stored in the CPU memory and get loaded into GPU-memory and then L1 memory of the multiprocessors. This fact, combined with the multiple-dispatch capabilities of julia language, that allow to specialize a function based on the input data type, allows inserting communication into the algorithm when needed, without adjusting the algorithm [16]. Algorithm 1 shows that the banddiag! function accepts a GPUorLargeMatrix, which can be either an AbstractGPUMatrix or a LargeMatrix, containing references to a CPU matrix and a GPU workspace. Algorithm 2 then demonstrates how the GETSMQRT function executes calculations for a GPU-resident matrix, or communications for a LargeMatrix, combined with calling back to the first function on the GPU workspace to execute calculations.

III. INITIAL RESULTS: FAST GPU-ACCELERATED SINGULAR VALUES

In the first phase of this research [17], we have implemented GPU kernels to execute the bandreduction from

Algorithm 2 Julia: inserting communication in GETSMQRT

```
function GETSMQRT!(A::AbstractGPUMatrix, ...)
  GETSMQRT_fused!(A, k)
  UNTSMQR_fused!(A, k)
end
function GETSMQRT!(A::LargeMatrix, ...)
  GETSMQRT!(A.data[k], ...)
  ... #communication CPU-GPU
  KernelAbstractions.@synchronize
end
```

Algorithm 1, and the further reduction to bidiagonal form. For the calculation of the singular values from the bidiagonal form, the least computationally expensive phase, the LAPACK divide-and-conquer algorithm is used [10]. We optimize the low-level GPU kernels for high performance and select hyperparameters that are adaptable to data type and hardware architecture. After optimizing the hyperparameters, we find that the performance of the unified abstract implementation approaches the vendor-optimized libraries well as shown in Figure 2: the unified function outperforms AMD’s rocSOLVER for all matrix sizes, cuSOLVER for all data sizes on consumer GPUs, and Intel’s oneMKL for matrix sizes over 2048. On high-performance NVIDIA GPUs, the unified singular value solver achieves 80-90% of the performance of cuSOLVER. Accuracy is maintained as well. With this benchmark, we have demonstrated the power of abstractions, where portability, end user accessibility, ease-of-use and performance all come together.

Fig. 2. The runtime ratio of the unified function to vendor libraries, with higher values indicating that the unified function is faster. The unified function outperforms rocSOLVER (MI250) for all data sizes, cuSOLVER on consumer GPUs (RTX4060), and Intel OneMKL at matrix sizes larger than 2048. It approaches cuSOLVER on HPC architectures (A100 and H100) at 80-90% at large matrix sizes, and at 50-80% for smaller data sizes. Figure from [17].

IV. CONCLUSION

We aim to develop a single generic future-proof, extensible Singular Value Decomposition across data precision, hardware vendor, hardware type, and data size. With our first results, we have demonstrated that abstract high-level implementations can achieve performance comparable to optimized vendor libraries. We have published the results of the performance engineering that led to these functions [2], [17]. Now, in future work, we are extending this work to out-of-core GPU-accelerated and multicore settings. This work aims to democratize HPC resources to increase accessibility of large-scale computing resources for all scientists and to reduce the development and maintenance time of linear algebra libraries.

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